

BLENDING AS A TYPE OF WORD-FORMATION IN MODERN ENGLISH

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Abstract: The focus of this article is a morphological process in English that is commonly referred to as (lexical) blending. The aim of this work is to identify new blends that have entered the English language. The descriptive approach, used in this article, is based on the division of the new blends and their structures in English.

Key words: Word Formation Processes, New Blends, Blending Structures, Overlapping, Clipping.

Blending is a frequent and productive word-formation process that can be defined as follows: blend- ing involves the coinage of a new lexeme by fusing parts of at least two other source words of which either one is shortened in the fusion and/or where there is some form of phonemic or graphemic overlap of the source words; some typical and well-known examples are given in (1).

- (1) a. br(eakfast) _x (l)unch → brunch
b. mot(or) _x (hot)el → motel

Blending has mainly been investigated in terms of the following questions:

1. How can blending be distinguished from other word-formation processes?
2. How can different kinds of blends be distinguished from one another?
3. Why do blends have the structure they have? Put differently, why are blends created the way they are?

Twasbrillig and the slithytoves

Did grye and gimble in the wabe

All mimsy were the borogoves,

And the momerathsoutgrabe.

When Alice asked Humpty Dumpty to explain the poem “Jabberwocky” to her, part of his explanation ran as follows:

“Well, <slithy> means lithe and slimmy. <Lithe> is the same as active. You see it is like a portmanteau – there are two meanings packed up into one word. Well then, <mimsy> is flimsy and miserable”.¹

¹Lewis Carroll, Alice`s adventures in Wonderland, 1865

A portmanteau is a word formed by blending elements from two or more distinct words to create one word with a new, combined meaning. This very process gave rise to its more familiar name – **a blend**.

The clearest examples of blends, however, are like the ones that Humpty Dumpty mentions, where the etymological root of the word is only clear when specifically explained.

Brillig→ bright, brilliant

Gimble→ gambol, tumble, amble

Blending can be considered... as the method of merging (connecting) parts of words into one new word as when «sm+oke» and «fog» derived from «smog».

Thus, “blending is compounding by means of curtailed (shortened) words. However, the clusters «sm» and «og» were morphemes only for the individual speaker who blended them while in terms of the linguistic system as recognized by the community, there are not signs at all. Blending, therefore, has no grammatical, but a stylistic status. The result of blending is... an unanalysable, simple word, not a motivated syntagma”².

Different Types Of Blends. There are many types of blends, based on how they are formed. Algeo, a linguist, proposed dividing blends into three groups:

A. Phonemic Overlap: a syllable or part of a syllable is shared between two words.

B. Clipping: the shortening of two words and then compounding them. In other words, clippings are reductions of longer forms, usually removing the end of the word, sometimes the beginning, or both beginning and ending together.

C. Phonemic Overlap And Clipping: shortening of two words to a shared syllable and then compounding. For all three types of blending, the majority of items combine their components sequentially: a segment of the first word is followed by a segment of the second word, with possible overlapping between the two segments.

Classification of blends

❖ Modified blends

Modified blends are blends in which “the first element modifies the second element”. They are transformable into a phrase with the first element serving as a modifier.

Breath + analyzer = breathalyzer

Motor + hotel = motel

Motor + camp = mocamp

❖ Meaningful blends

²Hans Marchand, The categories and types of present day English word formation, 1960

Meaningful blends “share properties of the referents of both elements”. They are transformable into a phrase consisting of the respective non-clipped stems combined by the conjunction “and”.

Boat + hotel = boatel

Breakfast + lunch = brunch

Modulator + demodulator = modem

Blends are coined not infrequently in scientific and technical language as a means of naming new things, as trade names in advertisements. Since blends break the rules of morphology they result in original combinations which catch quickly. Most of the blends have a colloquial flavour.

Exploring this area of new words can be a useful way of equipping students to deal, not only with the way English evolves and the new words they are likely to encounter but can also help them to understand the way the words they already know have evolved and developed. An understanding of this area can be a key skill in helping them to become more independent in their language learning and develop a greater enjoyment and engagement with the language.

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